

METHODOLOGY OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS IN INFORMATION EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article shows the analysis of the components and curriculum documents of training students and young people as future technology teachers. In addition, brief information about the importance and problems of using pedagogic-psychological factors in the training of a future technology teacher is given.*

Keywords: *reforms, technological science, future technology science teacher, technological education, methodical competence, methodical activity, professional skill.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, a continuous education system aimed at ensuring the effective organization of the process of training competent individuals and qualified specialists has been formed. In order to increase the effectiveness of the continuous education system, it is important to organize the activities of higher education institutions based on the educational process with a new content, based on advanced, democratic and humanitarian ideas. The main goal of reforms in the field of education is to create a continuous education system and update the content of education. Achieving this important goal requires a new approach to the organization of the educational process. After gaining independence, as a leading stage of the continuous education system, it is considered appropriate to search for factors that serve to increase the effectiveness of the pedagogical process in higher education institutions, to accelerate practical efforts to consistently implement the pedagogical technologies found to be acceptable factors.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. The Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Nos. 11-12 of 1997 and the collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan also discussed the training of future teachers. In 2014, Muslimov N.A., Ko'ysinov O.A, Abdurakhmanov Sh., Abdullaeva Q.M., Gaipova N.S. "Technologies of Methodological Competence Formation of Future Vocational Education Teachers". In the methodical manual, the technologies of forming the methodical competence of the future teachers of vocational education are widely disclosed. Joraev A.R., "Didactic possibilities of using programmed educational tools in the training of future technology teachers", published in issue 1 of 2019. Actual problems of modern science, education and training. The electronic journal also describes the importance and didactic possibilities of using programmed educational tools in the training of future technology teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. In the educational system, the process of training a person who is competent, thinks independently and consciously performs methodical activities, who can quickly adapt to the profession of a technology teacher, has a unique place. One of the main goals of the comprehensive reforms carried out in the continuous education system in our country today is to fully support young people in acquiring deep knowledge, realizing their talents, and at the same time forming their skills to prepare them for an independent life. is one of the

priority directions of the education system. It's no secret that we are not able to provide future technological education teachers with life skills, creative thinking and life professional skills. At the same time, it was found that various approaches to increase the effectiveness of training future technology teachers, the mechanism of ensuring the effectiveness of the "Technology Teaching Methodology" educational subject is insufficient.

By looking at the science of "Technological Education" as a vital need for future technological education teachers and youth education, we will not only prevent pupils and students from suffering from diseases of impatience and laziness, but also prepare them to become the owner of a certain profession in the future. We need to create the ground. Every year, thousands of students and young people graduate from about ten thousand general secondary schools operating in our country, and 25-30% of them continue to study at higher educational institutions. In order for 70-75 percent of graduating young people to start their work or learn a trade in professional educational institutions, the amount of hours allocated to the subject "Technology" taught in general secondary education schools, the content of the curriculum is similar to that of foreign countries. Requires radical revision and improvement based on education programs. Today, many pedagogues are conducting technology lessons using pedagogical technologies. Because the subject-pedagogical system of pedagogical technology consists of proving its conceptual foundations, clearly setting the goal, formulating the obtained results, choosing and structuring the educational material, choosing the pedagogical model, until their implementation, and designing them to evaluate their alternative and efficiency level, and the lesson serves for the effect.

First, let's clarify the concept of "technology". This word entered the science in 1872 in connection with technical development, and it is formed from two Greek words - "technos" (techne) skill, art and "logos" (logos) - science words. Today, educating young students, that is, training them at the level of mature qualified specialists who meet the requirements of state education standards in all aspects, is one of the urgent tasks of our country. This is mentioned in the national personnel training program. "The state policy in the field of personnel training envisages the formation of a well-rounded individual citizen through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person. One of the most basic constitutional rights of a citizen is the right to acquire knowledge, to demonstrate creative abilities, to develop intellectually, and to realize the right to work in one's profession. The Law "On Education" provides for the selection of forms and types of educational and vocational training, as well as quality education through the standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education provides for the right and broad opportunities for continuous professional development, appropriate retraining if necessary.

Information and communication technologies are widely used in the teaching of all subjects. The lessons of technological science apply general didactic principles for other subjects at school, but also have their own characteristics. Pupils and students are engaged not only in the activity of knowing, but also in the activity of creation. The science of technology serves not as an object of simple study of labor tools and processes, but as an instructional tool, didactic material, and a technical tool of education that activates students' practical work. The use of modern methodical competence, pedagogical and psychological technologies of education in the process of teaching technology has its own characteristics. It is important to use advanced and modern methods of teaching, to apply new informational and pedagogical technologies in order for students to fully master the science of technology. Use of textbooks, educational and methodical manuals, handouts, electronic materials, virtual stands and models and mock-ups of machines in working condition in mastering the science, watching TV and radio broadcasts on technology science, studied work to perform methods, to study the information given in magazines and

newspapers, to use media tools to find terms related to technology science, to be able to use information sources to perform didactic assignments; it is important to follow media culture when opening files. In the process of teaching this subject, when we use modern information and communication technologies of education, in the practical training sessions on science, when we show presentations with the help of modern computer technologies, students will gain deeper imagination and knowledge by seeing. The use of information and communication technologies in technology classes also gives a great positive result. Previously, in technology classes, the teacher showed the students one by one the process of practical training and the process of making items, which took too much time, and sometimes the teacher had to re-demonstrate. Today, using information and communication technologies, recorded labor operations, video lessons are shown to students, allowing the teacher to easily monitor the work of students, and significantly increase the level of knowledge of students. Another important aspect of the use of pedagogical and psychological technologies is the formation of various labor skills in the form of a "Master Class" demonstration of training sessions performed by qualified carpenters, plumbers, cooks, tailors and craftsmen in various fields, provides an opportunity to start career guidance. Above, we have shown some of the use of pedagogical and psychological technologies in technology classes.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, if pedagogical and psychological technologies are widely used in technology lessons, the quality of technology education lessons will be effective. This is especially important for future technology education teachers to think independently, to improve their professional skills, to develop their creative abilities, and to carry out other organizational and methodological work.

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